

Repository Profile:

RCAAP and PTCRIS

About RCAAP

RCAAP (Repositório Científico de Acesso Aberto de Portugal) is the main instrument for [open access development in Portugal](#). The initiative was initiated in July 2008 and is currently carried out by [FCT \(Foundation for Science and Technology\)](#) together with the [University of Minho](#). RCAAP offers a wide range of services in order to fulfill its OA mission. The most well known electronic service is the hosting service of institutional repositories ([SARI](#)) but other services are made available by RCAAP as well, such as: hosted scientific journals ([SARC](#)), data repositories ([SARDC](#)), and a shared repository ([Comum](#)). Both hosted and local OA resources are aggregated in the [RCAAP Portal](#).

RCAAP portfolio service

RCAAP Goals

RCAAP has three main objectives:

1. Increase the visibility, accessibility and dissemination of Portuguese research results;
2. Facilitate access to information about Portuguese scientific output - The interoperability of the repository with other information systems from the Portuguese scientific infrastructure can also facilitate the access to information about Portuguese scientific output;
3. Integrate Portugal in the wide range of international initiatives in this domain – RCAAP allows Portugal to integrate a wide range of international initiatives in this domain and facilitates the interoperability and cooperation with research centers, funding bodies, and higher education institutions in Europe and all over the world.

Critical success factors

RCAAP critical success factors are:

- The Governance model – RCAAP responsibilities are distributed based on partner's expertise (coordination, infrastructures, scientific, technical). Every partner contributes with what he knows best;
- The service model (hosted or cloud based) which frees the institutions to carry out core activities leaving electronic services management for a team of experts;
- Right approach on guidelines, standards and interoperability;
- stic and integrated view of the movement, promoting open access dissemination, training and developing national and international partnerships for the expansion of services provided.

Facts and Figures

www.rcaap.pt

National OA Initiative
42 Institutional Repositories
1 shared repository with 30 institutions
30 Scientific journals
More than 185.000 OA docs

Follow us:

RCAAP Roadmap

RCAAP developments for 2014/2015 will be focused on three main areas:

- Long-Term Digital Preservation: in 2014 RCAAP started a program to self-assess its compliancy with ISO: 16363(Trustworthy Repositories Audit & Certification). This program covers hosted IR's only;
- Support FCT's OA Policy: RCAAP is implementing mechanisms both to help researchers to comply and to monitor FCT's OA Policy adoption;
- Implement added value services: RCAAP will leverage its network/ services maturity with opportunities like PTCRIS (Portuguese Current Research Information Systems) aiming to deliver added value services for the community.

Repository Profile:

RCAAP and PTCRIS

About PTCRIS

PTCRIS is a program that aims to ensure the **creation** and **sustained** development of a **national integrated information ecosystem** (**PTCRIS**) to support research management. The program was announced on May 2014 and the overall coordination is FCT's responsibility. PTCRIS is an ecosystem of research information systems (RIS), some already in place, and others to be developed. It also includes the ones concerned with outcomes and outputs (products, patents and publications). Publications will be handled by a **national registry of scientific output** and OA publications will be, of course, handled by **RCAAP**.

ORCID adoption

FCT was one of the first funders to massively adopt ORCID: 90% of researchers which are responsible for 90% of research outputs of the last 5 years have an ORCID profile.

PTCRIS's foundations - standards

PTCRIS portfolio of standards to which modules of the ecosystem will have to comply:

PTCRIS's Goals

PTCRIS's Goals are:

1. **Define the regulatory framework** to adopt by the various systems
2. **Coordinate** FCT's systems integration in accordance with the standards framework
3. **Coordinate external systems** integration with FCT (national and international) according to the standards framework
4. **Support and promote** the use of the systems of the PT-CRIS within the **community**.

PTCRIS's Roadmap

Based on risk, impact and cost assessment, PTCRIS defined five priorities for the short/medium term:

1. To reduce the burden of research output management (ORCID HUB);
2. To reduce the burden of CV management (ORCID HUB & National CV platform);
3. Create an organizations database (ISNI / Ringgold based);
4. Create a scientific infrastructure database
5. Create a CERIF "point of true database" with people, projects, publications, patents, products, funding, organizations, etc.

ORCID as a central HUB

CERIF point of truth database

CRIS and Open Access synergies/opportunities

Looking at RCAAP and PTCRIS it is not difficult to imagine a wide number of synergies and opportunities. Here are some examples that we would like to explore in the short/medium term:

- Researchers and Organizations ID's will univocally identify authors and organizations. The next version of repositories and journal management software will be ORCID aware. Funding information – PTCRIS, through its funding database (CERIF compliant), will be able to provide the authority control for funding. This mechanism will be used to allow researchers to comply with FCT's OA policy by adding funding information in the deposit process.
- Scientific output reporting services with the aim to make institutions and organizations' life easier by allowing reporting at the organizational, unit, grant or research level.
- Added value services – The adoption of standards by each PTCRIS system will allow, progressively, to turn relative information (info that depends of the system where it is stored) into absolute information (info independent of the system where it is stored) converting therefore information silos into knowledge. Once this is done, added value services like research portals (i.e. VIVO) or DSpace-CRIS will be set up easily.